

LIPID PROFILE ALTERATIONS IN POLYCYSTIC OVARY SYNDROME

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17855170>

Keywords

PCOS, lipid profile, Pakistan.

Article History

Received: 09 October 2025

Accepted: 15 November 2025

Published: 29 November 2025

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Abstract

Background: Poly-cystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) is a most common hormonal disorder affecting females during reproductive age. The prevalence in Pakistan is 52 %. PCOS enhance a woman's risk of type 2 diabetes, infertility, cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes, anxiety, and depression.

Objective: - This study analyzed biochemical parameters related to lipid profiles in PCOS patients compared to a control group, aiming to predict and detect dyslipidemia in these groups.

Methodology: - A comparative case-control study was conducted at Shaikh Zayad Hospital in Larkana, Pakistan, from March 2023 to November 2025, involving 430 females—215 with (PCOS) and 215 healthy group. On the bases of Rotterdam Criteria participant were selected, with clinical history including anthropometric measurements, menstrual history, and symptoms of hirsutism, and menstrual history. Metabolic parameters, specifically lipid profiles, were measured and compared between the PCOS patients and the healthy group.

Result: - The average age for PCOS cases was 29.29 years with a BMI of 27.66 kg/m², while controls were 30.87 years with a BMI of 22.76 kg/m². Infertility affected 62.90% of PCOS individuals, particularly in younger women with higher BMI and tobacco use. Dyslipidemia was present in 60.46% of Pakistani PCOS women versus 11.62% in controls. Key associations with PCOS included elevated BMI, inactivity, junk food consumption, sleep deprivation, and lack of exercise. Symptoms commonly reported were hirsutism, acne, and menstrual irregularities. Statistical analysis was using SPSS v26, and $p < 0.05$.

Conclusion: - PCOS is associated with obesity, hirsutism, acne, irregular periods, high BMI, and raised diastolic blood pressure. Patients exhibit elevated dyslipidemia, especially with elevated serum LDL (22.79%), low HDL (49.30%), triglycerides (53.02%), and cholesterol (60.46%). PCOS patients have a much higher TC/HDL ratio (>6.67:1) than controls (3.38:1), suggesting a higher risk of heart disease. For successful therapy, early screening and a multidisciplinary management strategy are advised

INTRODUCTION

Polycystic ovarian syndrome (PCOS) is a diverse hormonal illness presented with ovarian cysts, infertility, menstrual problems, skin problem, obesity and depression which disturbed personal/social life of a woman. In 1935, Stein and Leventhal published the first identified PCOS woman. It is the most frequent endocrine problem among ladies of fertility age globally (1).

The prevalence are 5% and 26%, In Pakistan 52 % which is significantly high as compared to rest of world. As the World Health Organization (WHO) assessment revealed around 116 million ladies (3.4%) are plagued by PCOS globally. (2).

Rotterdam was used, depending on the diagnostic criteria. According to specialized society standards, the clinical assessment of PCOS is commonly based on the presence of at least two of the following three criteria: poly-cystic ovaries on scan, hyperandrogenism (clinical or biochemical), and persistent anovulation (3). Infertility, obstetric complications (abortions, IUGR, IUD), depression, metabolic syndrome, liver disease, cardiovascular diseases, and endometrial cancer are among the complications linked to PCOS (4).

Hyperandrogenism, persistent anovulation, Hyperinsulinemia, and IR are not the only metabolic problems impacting people with PCOS. But infertility, early pregnancy losses, and intrauterine fatalities also square of pcos. Metabolic syndrome and insulin resistance are both well-known.

Female with PCOS often have altered lipid profile, a disease known as dyslipidemia. This atherogenic lipid profile comprises raised levels of total cholesterol, triglycerides, low-density lipoprotein (LDL), and lower levels of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) (6). Regular lipid profile screening is crucial for women with PCOS because these lipid abnormalities raise the risk of long-term metabolic and cardiovascular disorders and are linked to the insulin resistance frequent in PCOS (7).

We compared blood lipid levels (dyslipidemia) between the healthy and PCOS ladies in this paper, discussing the relationship between altered lipid parameters and aberrant metabolic states, detection of an increased risk of atherosclerosis and cardiovascular disease (8).

a dearth of studies on a certain age, gender, or ethnic group, among other demographic groups. A study's shortcomings in its methodologies or data collection/analysis, which might lead to gaps in understanding.

METHODOLOGY:-

This Comparative case-control investigation case control performed at the Shakhzyad Women's Hospital, Larkana. For a period of one and a half years, 430 women with PCOS were selected from OPD 215 and the control group 215. The study protocol was accepted by the Biochemistry Institute at Sindh University, Jamshoro, and Shakhzyad women Hospital Larkana, Ethics Committee, which awarded complete ethical approval for the trial in September 2024.

Before patients were selected in the trial, a thorough history of their current symptoms (infertility, obesity, menstruation issues, acne, and hirsutism), history of diabetes, renal illnesses, thyroid disorders, and family history of pre-eclampsia or early pregnancy losses was obtained. The study excluded participants with obesity, diabetes, renal disease, cushion's syndrome, or thyroid disease based on their body mass index at the time of enrollment.

PCOS women (215) 17-43 years old were identified at their initial visit to Shakhzyad women hospital Larkana with all inclusive criteria and 215 aged (20-47 y) control group. An acceptable informed permission from the ladies were taken from both groups pcos/healthy. The techniques followed were in conformity with the ethical norms of this by Biochemistry institute Sindh University Jamshoro, and Shakhzyad women hospital Larkana, Ethics Committee, which granted complete ethical approval for the trial in September 2024. Both the patients and I provided funding for the investigations.

The study involved collecting 3-4 CC blood samples in Vacutainers after 12-14 hours of fasting from patients during days 3-5 of their menstrual cycle. The samples were processed at multiple laboratories in Larkana, and the lipid profile was analyzed using an AU480 biochemistry autoanalyzer. Results were compared to the guidelines set by the NCEP's Adult Treatment Panel III. The lipid profile included measurements for (TC), (TG), HDL, and with LDL

calculated using the Friedewald formula: $LDL = TC - HDL - (TG/5)$. Sample values were preserved at $-80^{\circ}C$ for further analysis, with standard enzymatic colorimetric techniques employed for TC, TG, and HDL measurement.

By using MS-Excel and SPSS version 25 data were analyzed, as frequency and percentage were reported as qualitative data, and quantitative data presented as mean \pm standard deviation (SD) and P-value. Statistical tests included independent T-test, Odds ratio, and one-way ANOVA for lipid profile comparison, with significance set at $p < 0.05$, and confidence intervals calculated at the 95% level. Chi-square test was also performed for p-value assessment.

RESULT:

In a demographic profile of women with PCOS, the average age was 29.29 years, while the control group averaged 30.87 years as shown in table 1.0. Of the participants, 185 PCOS women were married and 29

unmarried, compared to 211 married and 4 unmarried in the control group. Parity showed 1.33 alive babies (SD \pm 1.68) and 0.47 abortions (SD \pm 0.60) in PCOS, versus 4.59 alive babies (SD \pm 3.13) and 1.21 abortions (SD \pm 1.48) in controls. The average BMI for PCOS was 27.66 (SD \pm 5.59) compared to 22.76 (SD \pm 4) in controls, with a significant difference noted ($p < 0.001$). Blood pressure readings indicated systolic values of 128.50 (SD \pm 24.78) and diastolic 106.23 (SD \pm 19.57) in PCOS, while controls had systolic of 114.39 (SD \pm 15.77) and diastolic 77.35 (SD \pm 6.76). The lipid profiles showed that PCOS women had higher triglycerides (209.13 SD \pm 57.8), cholesterol (217.73 SD \pm 40.28), and lower HDL (32.61 SD \pm 15.27) compared to controls, who had triglycerides of 121.25 (SD \pm 21.37), cholesterol of 166.13 (SD \pm 37.06), and HDL of 49.02 (SD \pm 8.84).

TABLE 1. DEMOGRAPHIC PROFILE OF PATIENTS PCOS AND CONTROL.

Variables (n = 430)	PCOS (n = 215) Mean \pm SD	Control (n = 215) Mean \pm SD	P-value
Age (years)	29.29	29.29	
Marital Status	185 Married	211 Married	
	30 Unmarried	4 Unmarried	
BMI	27.66 \pm 5.59	22.76 \pm 4.00	<0.001
SBP (mmHg)	128.50 \pm 24.78	114.39 \pm 15.77	<0.001
DBP (mmHg)	106.23 \pm 19.57	77.35 \pm 6.76	0.001

The study examined 215 patients with polycystic ovary syndrome (PCOS) and 215 control participants as show in table 2.0 finding significant differences in various health aspects. The average age of the PCOS group was 29.29 years, while the controls averaged 30.87 years. Menstrual irregularities were prevalent in PCOS patients: only 12.55% had normal cycles, compared to 68.5% of controls. Notably, 23.25% of PCOS patients experienced amenorrhea, and 60% faced oligo/hypomenorrhea. Infertility rates were substantially higher in the PCOS group, with 15%

experiencing primary infertility and 68.5% secondary infertility, versus 4.2% and 7% in controls, respectively. Additionally, 40.4% of PCOS patients reported hirsutism, and 28.8% had acne or oily skin, compared to 9.7% and 5.1% in controls. A family history of PCOS was noted in 33% of patients, and diabetes mellitus was reported in 17.2% of the PCOS group versus 13% of controls. Lastly, acanthosis nigricans were in 7.4% of PCOS compared to 2.3% in healthy.

TABLE 2. CLINICAL AND ANTHROPOMETRIC FEATURES OF PATIENTS PCOS AND CONTROL

Variables	PCOS Patients (n = 215)	Controls (n = 215)
Age (years)	29.29 \pm 6.34	30.87 \pm 6.34
1. Menstrual Irregularity	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
• Normal cycle	27 (12.55%)	129 (68.5%)

• Amenorrhea	50 (23.25%)	2 (0.9%)
• Oligo/Hypomenorrhea	129 (60%)	33 (15.4%)
• Menorrhagia	9 (4.18%)	34 (15.9%)
2. Infertility		
• Primary	32 (15.0%)	9 (4.2%)
• Secondary	146 (68.5%)	15 (7.0%)
• No infertility	19 (8.9%)	181 (84.9%)
• Unmarried	14 (6.5%)	8 (3.7%)
3. Hirsutism		
• No	128 (59.5%)	194 (90.2%)
• Yes	87 (40.4%)	21 (9.7%)
4. Acne / Oily Skin		
• No	152 (70.6%)	204 (94.8%)
• Yes	63 (28.8%)	11 (5.1%)
Family History		
• PCOS	71 (33.0%)	21 (9.7%)
• Diabetes Mellitus	37 (17.2%)	28 (13.0%)
Acanthosis Nigricans		
• No	199 (92.5%)	210 (97.6%)
• Yes	16 (7.4%)	5 (2.3%)

The study found a prevalence of Polycystic Ovary Syndrome (PCOS) at 26.7%, higher in younger women aged 17-29 (34.1%) compared to those aged 30-43 (19.0%) as shown in Table 3.0. The average age of PCOS cases was 29.29 years with a BMI of 27.66 kg/m², while healthy had mean age of 30.87 years and a BMI of 22.76 kg/m². Infertility affected 62.9% of participants, more prevalent in younger women with higher BMI and tobacco use. PCOS patients exhibited increased dyslipidemia, with

higher levels of LDL and triglycerides, and lower HDL. Associated factors included higher BMI (p = 0.02), physical inactivity (p = 0.01), junk food consumption (p = 0.006), and sleep deprivation (p = 0.01). Conditions such as menstrual irregularities, acne, and hirsutism were more common in the PCOS. Blood pressure measurements indicated higher values in PCOS patients. The data were analyzed using SPSS v26, with statistical significance at p < 0.05.

Table 3. Characteristics of the PCOS and control group

Characteristic	PCOS GROUP (n=215) Mean ± S D	Control group (n=215) Mean ± S D	P-value
Age(year)	29.29	30.87	
BMI	27.66 ± 5.59	22.76 (SD ±4)	0.001
SBP	128.50 ±24.78	114.39 ± 15.77	0.001
DBP	106.23 ± 19.57	77.35 ± 6.76.	0.001
LIPID PROFILE			

Triglyceride(mg/dl)	209.13(SD ± 57.8),	121.25 (SD ± 21.37)	<0.002
Cholesterol (mg/dl)	217.73 (SD ± 40.28),	166.13 (SD ± 37.06),	<0.001
HDL (mg/dl)	32.61 (SD ± 15.27)	49.02 (SD ± 8.84)	<0.001
LDL (mg/dl)	138.43 (SD ± 16.00),	149.65 (SD ± 21.19),	0.001
VLDL (mg/dl)	43.25 (SD ± 6.87).	25.12 (SD ± 5.97)	0.000

DISCUSSION:-

The WHO estimates that PCOS affects more than 116 million ladies worldwide (3.4%) (23). In our study; Incidence of pco in our medical center in 6 years OPD bases-from 2019-2024 were 1.39% in OPD patients 438058 women. It is no longer recognized just as a disease of ovary. Increased BMI and IR are linked to this common metabolic syndrome and endocrine disorder (9).

In this study we compared the blood lipid profiles of healthy (215) with PCOS (215) women. There was a high incidence of dyslipidemia in PCOS patients (60.46%), and the control group 11.62%), and the most prevalent was lowered HDL, accounting for 49.30% in pcos and 12.09% in control. The ratios of TG/HDL were high with pcos (6.67 1) and control (3.38:1), with an increasing changes with BMI, which may create an increased risk of cardiovascular illnesses reported in PCOS women.

The majority of research on dyslipidemia and PCOS has focused mostly on cholesterol and triglyceride (TG) levels. Women diagnosed with PCOS display a lipid profile characterized by higher TG levels and lower levels of HDL (10). These alterations are consistent with the normal lipid penal that is frequently associated with insulin resistance. Increased liver secretion of VLDL particles causes elevated plasma triglyceride (TG) concentrations. The exchange of TGs for cholesterol esters (CE) is then facilitated by cholesterol ester (CE) transfer protein activity. As a consequence of this mechanism, triglyceride-enriched HDL particles decay more rapidly, while CE-enriched VLDL particles change into small, dense LDL particles (11).

Diabetes was more likely to occur in PCOS patients with poor glucose metabolism. In addition, several studies also established that T2DM was often comorbid with lipid abnormalities, and the higher

atherosclerotic arterial disease risk in patients with diabetes was ascribed to abnormalities in lipid

metabolism (12). For instance, macrophages may phagocytose the excess plasma LDL and invade the sub-endothelium, contributing to the atherosclerosis cascade (13). However, due to the limited total number of patients (n=160 and n=44), the increased level of LDL was not significant in either the dysglycemia or diabetes subgroups in our investigation. Furthermore, more research is required to better understand the precise mechanism of lipid abnormalities causing Hyperinsulinemia, insulin resistance, dysglycemia, and type 2 diabetes in PCOS, as well as to develop more effective dysmetabolism treatments (14). Patients diagnosed with PCOS could develop abdominal obesity and glucose metabolism difficulties. Pre-diabetic conditions are common in them. It is vital to ensure that the treatment approach does not exacerbate existing issues. Prevention of further problems is also required to avoid the development of metabolic syndrom(15). According to the study's findings, increasing physical activity can progressively lower the incidence of PCOS; these protective benefits can be multiplied twelve times by increasing daily physical exercise intensity (16). The strength of our research resides in its sample size as large, which strengthens the generality of the findings. By including a considerable number of participants, we were able to lower the possibility of sampling bias and boost the statistical power of the study. The employment of Spear-man correlation analysis allows for the evaluation of non-linear correlations, providing a more nuanced view of the issue. Furthermore, our work adds to the body of literature by examining the relationship between lipid profiles and the FSH/LH ratio in several high BMI

groups, especially the overweight or obese subgroup (17).

This research is limited by a small sample size. Difficulties in recruiting healthy controls matched for age and BMI were noted. Additionally, confounding factors like insulin resistance, dietary fat intake, and androgen levels were not considered, and the absence of total cholesterol assessment restricts the interpretation of results. Future research should include a larger sample size and assess total cholesterol levels.

Conclusion:

It was found that PCOS symptoms, including hirsutism, acne, irregular menstruation, and obesity, correlate with high BMI and diastolic blood pressure. The study identified dyslipidemia in PCOS patients, marked by hypercholesterolemia (60.46%), hypertriglyceridemia (53.02%), low HDL (49.30%), and abnormal serum LDL (22.79%). Moreover, the TC/HDL ratio in PCOS patients was significantly elevated (>6.67:1), which indicates a higher risk of atherosclerosis and heart disease compared to the control group (3.38:1). A multidisciplinary approach for effective management should be recommended.

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